

AUTOMOTIVE COMPOSITES CONSORTIUM FOCAL PROJECT III: ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF A COMPOSITE INTENSIVE BODY-IN-WHITE STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

Designers of composite materials applications are always attempting to make them cost competitive with steel. Achieving cost parity for a high volume automotive body-in-white (BIW) structure, whilst achieving contemporary structural performance standards and 60% weight savings to meet 80 mpg is an even greater challenge. These were the objectives set for Focal Project 3 (FP3) by the Automotive Composites Consortium (ACC) of the United States Council for Automotive Research (USCAR). FP3 was devised to push technology to its limits and beyond - to act as a catalyst to focus further research on facilitating manufacturing techniques in line with the design characteristics required for optimum efficiency. The ACC selected Engenuity, Ltd. to undertake the design feasibility and analysis study due to their proactive involvement in the development of automotive and motorsport composite structures. This work is part of a larger research and development collaboration between USCAR and the United States Department of Energy's Office of Advanced Automotive Technologies.

FP3 started with a baseline BIW structure from the Chrysler JA (Dodge Stratus/Chrysler Cirrus/Plymouth Breeze circa late 1990's) vehicle series. The statement of work required the interior and closure package to remain the same, which dictated that the exterior style was very similar. Consistent with the targeted reduction in vehicle mass, a smaller engine package was allowed along with a lighter weight rear suspension configuration. The torsion and bending stiffness, durability performance and crashworthiness were all assessed during the analysis and development of the structure. Early conceptual evaluation improved the structural efficiency over the base vehicle (for composite material usage) by 200% giving the project the basis from which to develop a feasible solution.

A survey of different manufacturing methods was undertaken and the opportunities and current limitations considered - however a key project objective was to identify what improvements in process were required in order to achieve the overall objectives. An all carbon composite structure was selected over a hybrid system, as the opportunities of using the specific strength and stiffness attributes for carbon structures were only restricted due to manufacturing process rather than a technical consideration.

The design that evolved during the FP3 design process relied heavily on advanced optimisation processes for both random and orientated fibre architectures. These analysis techniques allowed for different panel definitions and construction methods to be assessed expediently on the evolving design. Although explicit analysis techniques are not yet robust for predicting the performance of crushing carbon fibre structures, analysis methods were employed from the motorsports industry to create a stable platform for the crushable elements to efficiently manage the energy of a frontal impact without premature collapse of the passenger compartment structure.

Durability simulations indicate that industry accepted loadcases will be endured and that energy management can match the crashworthiness of steel structures. These two issues became the dominant design issues, which once satisfied, led to a final design that exceeded the torsional target by 200% and bending by 80%. The weight of the complete BIW structure is predicted to be 86 kg a 67% mass savings on a conventional structure. There are, however, significant activities required to focus development on achieving high volume production on thin and variable thickness panels. The achievement of these manufacturing capabilities will allow the weight and material costs to be kept to a minimum in the random fibre architectures.

INTRODUCTION

Since its formation in 1988, the Automotive Composite Consortium (ACC) has been working to advance composite materials technology for high volume automotive applications with the intention of further introducing it to the industry. The Partnership for a New Generation of Vehicles (PNGV), identified requirements for future vehicles. In order to achieve 80mpg, the PNGV fuel economy target, manufacturers will have to reduce by half the mass of both body and chassis from today's standard six-passenger sedan.

Automakers have dreamed about affordable structural composites for decades. Composites are light and can be formed into complex shapes that can do the same job as many welded metal stampings. Until recently, composites' high cost and long manufacturing cycle times have limited the opportunities for structural composite use in the auto industry to a handful of supercars and Le Mans prototypes for the road. Without doubt the practical lessons learnt from using composites in these applications will serve to bring mass production composites to the market earlier.

The average curb weight of today's standard sedan is over 1450 kg, of which body and closures are 514 kg. The PNGV goal is to drop the curb weight to under 907 kg with the body down to 257 kg.

Participants in the PNGV study have indicated, "a variety of materials are being considered for tomorrow's sedans. The materials most likely to be used in appreciable quantities are aluminium, steel, magnesium and polymer composites". In prototype body structures, current technology nearly reaches the 50 percent weight savings goal in aluminium. Cost, however, is a major issue, so automotive engineers are pursuing a variety of programs intended to make aluminium and its manufacturing processes more affordable.

Polymer composites offer a number of advantages over aluminium: they are lightweight, strong, corrosion resistant, easily moulded and offer design flexibility. But manufacturing and materials costs need to be reduced; economical recycling methods must be developed; and design, analysis, production, assembly and joining technologies need to be further refined.

The wide variety of projects has demonstrated on many occasions the need to avoid thinking of composites as a "black metal". Accepting the published specific performance of composite is really missing the point. The advantages of composite materials can only be truly realised if designs are tailored for composite materials.

OBJECTIVES

The Focal Project 3 specified the overall goal of designing, analysing and building a composite-intensive BIW that demonstrates;

Manufacturing processes to enable production volumes exceeding 100,000 per annum

Minimum 60% mass savings with respect to a steel baseline BIW

Equivalent package space as the baseline

Equivalent or greater static bending and torsional stiffness performance as the baseline

Satisfactory durability performance

Manufacturability at a comparable price to baseline

The mass target of a 60% weight saving was set on the unglazed JA BIW mass of 262 kg, giving a target of 105 kg. It was noted that if other parts, e.g. bonnet, became incorporated in the structure then the weight reduction will be based on the total of all the parts incorporated into the composite BIW structure. The previous composite JA study conducted by the PNGV team with Multimatic Technical Centre produced an 89 kg BIW structure with the use of aerospace composites, aluminium honeycomb and an aluminium front end [Prsa].

MATERIALS AND PROCESS REVIEW

Whilst early conceptual studies were underway, a comprehensive materials and process review was undertaken to identify the current state of the art. This information allowed design parameters to be specified for the development phase of the project, and also served at any early stage to stimulate development of the processing techniques for a number of the candidate processes to be more applicable to the needs of the Focal Project.

The ACC had previously demonstrated the P4 fully automated preforming process for low cost, low scrap, moderately high volume (for this case 50,000 units per year) glass fibre reinforced composite structures during its Focal Project 2 pickup truck box program [Denton]. For more details on the P4 process refer to [Chavka]. Due to its speed and low material scrap rates, this preforming method was selected as one of the key processes to further develop for carbon fibre to utilize in Focal Project 3. Mass savings of up to 30% versus steel have been demonstrated when using chopped, random glass fibre reinforced composites. In order to achieve higher mass savings (i.e., 50-70%), carbon fibre composites must be utilized. In support of this project, the ACC is investigating the fabrication of chopped carbon fibre preforms fabricated using the P4 preforming process and molded via Structural Reaction Injection Molding (SRIM).

Each part of the body-in-white design was evaluated for candidate manufacturing methods. Some of the final panel designs may not be from P4 but may utilize other high-speed automated processes instead. However, the majority of parts, including the first demonstration part will utilize the P4/SRIM process.

CONFIDENCE IN COMPOSITES ANALYSIS

The linear static finite element analysis codes have had the facility to process multi-laminar composites for several decades. The Nastran PCOMP has remained largely unchanged and, given the correct inputs, has given a reliable predictive capability. The correct inputs have not always been that easy to get into the Nastran input deck, and when previously the construction got complex, defining the laminates was a laborious task and perhaps only conducted on large aircraft programmes. Having undertaken a significant analysis study on a road going supercar in the early 1990's, Engenuity personnel devised and commissioned the coding of an advanced ply management pre/post processor for Patran V2.5. This was later taken into mainstream support by MSC in the form of Patran Laminate Modeller.

Engenuity has employed this software on a diverse spectrum of composite projects, which have allowed experience in the predictive capability to be honed and extended to ever more complex and leading edge solutions. The most important aspect to achieve advanced analysis is the skill and experience of the analysts. The team at Engenuity have employed their collective knowledge and intuition to develop a state of the art composite analysis resource.

BIW OPTIMISATION

The first stage in each phase of the project was to optimise the body structure to meet the stiffness targets and minimise the mass. This not only ensured that the stiffness targets were met in an efficient manner, but also provides a good baseline model for both global modes and durability analyses, which require similarly reinforced areas of the structure. For maximum computational efficiency, certain details were left out of the model at this stage such as bond flanges, flange radius, inserts, etc. These features were incorporated prior to final optimisation.

For the optimisation stage of the analysis it is assumed that all panels can be of varying thickness. This gives the opportunity to optimise the thickness distribution in every panel, which is achieved using the two stage optimisation process described below.

ANALYSIS DEVELOPMENT PROCEDURE

FREE-FORM OPTIMISATION

Free-form optimisation was carried out using Altair Optistruct Topology optimisation routines. This procedure looks at which areas of the structure are the most highly stressed and moves material to these areas from less highly stressed areas, such that the targets are met and the mass of the structure is minimised. This process is then iterated until convergence criteria are met and the structure is considered optimised. The minimum thickness parameter is set to reflect the process capabilities, ensuring that holes are not grown in the panels. This parameter affects the final mass of the optimised structure. During Phase 1 of the project the effect of the minimum thickness on the final optimised mass was the subject of a sensitivity study. The model is glazed at this stage but the glazing is designated as non-design material. The result of the analysis is sets of elements grouped by a function of their structural contribution under the stiffness load cases. At this stage the panels to which the elements belong is irrelevant and the groups have relative, rather than true thicknesses.

THICKNESS OPTIMISATION

Each group of elements from the first stage of the optimisation is then assigned a unique thickness. Altair Hyperopt, using MSC Nastran as a solver, was then used to optimise the value of these thicknesses to meet the stiffness targets and minimise the mass of the structure.

During Phase 1 these techniques were used to compare the separate concepts being considered and to help develop the individual concepts. The whole model was considered to be made from chopped carbon during this phase of work. For Phases 2 and 3 more was known about the panel breakdown and the likely manufacturing techniques. This enabled the minimum thickness value to be set more appropriately for each panel depending on the process limitations. In some cases where it was understood that panels would be constructed out of woven materials of a constant lay-up, these were specified and subsequently excluded from the design optimisation.

CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT

Although the target vehicle package was identified at the outset, considerable effort was applied to generating novel BIW concepts, which incorporated the advantages of composites rather than being clones of conventional structures. The ability to consolidate many panels and reinforcements in complex shapes with variable in and out of plane properties allows for the positive aspects of composites to be exploited to the fullest extent.

The results showed that through using automated optimisation techniques the efficiency of the structure could be greatly improved from the baseline BIW arrangement. The stiffness of the best concepts was about 80% more efficient in bending and 200% in torsion.

Even though the structure had only been optimised for stiffness, it was also checked for modal and durability performance with good results. The modal analyses showed that if core was not used, panels could be swaged to increase their first natural frequencies to acceptable levels without preclusive mass penalties. The investigation into the durability performance showed that the majority of the structure could withstand the durability loads. Only minor local reinforcements would be required to achieve full compliance.

The first phase of work resulted in a concept BIW mass of around 60 kg, which provided great confidence that the target mass was achievable, even though there were crash and abuse

JA Baseline

Engenuity Proposal

No B-pillar and Enlarged

No Body Inner

Enlarged Rockers, Pillars and Cantrail

load cases still to be considered. This also did not take into account the mass of inserts, adhesive or core. The panel draft and flange angles were also known to have a large effect on the maximum achievable section sizes. Following the initial review meetings the minimum draft and flange angles were set at 7 and 45 degrees respectively. Initial modelling during this phase showed the flange angle constraints would have a significant negative impact on the performance of the structure and they

were consequently relaxed. Zero degree flanges enabled peel resistant flange arrangements to be developed for the front upper longitudes.

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	Mass (kg)	Specific Bending Efficiency	Specific Torsion Efficiency
JA Baseline Optimised	102	52	84
Engenuity Baseline	62	85	241
No B-Pillar	62	84	222
No Bodyside Inner	74	70	184
Enlarged sills, pillars and cantrail	58	89	260

Phase 1 showed that the minimum achievable panel thickness had a significant influence on the BIW mass. It was agreed that it was reasonable to expect that the SRIM process likely to be used in conjunction with the P4 preform could be developed to produce large 1.5mm thick parts.

SENSITIVITY

In addition to model checking sensitivity procedures, two factors were assessed in order to identify the key weight drivers and the robustness of the design to manufacturing variances. A minimum thickness sensitivity study looked at what could be gained if the minimum achievable panel thickness was reduced. It was found for Concept 01, that reducing the minimum panel thickness from 1.5 mm to 1.0 mm reduced the stiffness optimised BIW mass from 61 kg to 52 kg, representing a potential weight saving of 15%. The exact nature of the adhesive bead likely to be used on the proposed vehicle was not known. In order to rule out the effects of slight variation in the dimensions of the adhesive bead, the same model was re-run with modified material properties for the adhesive.

	Percentage change in stiffness	
	Half Adhesive Properties	Double Adhesive Properties
Bending Stiffness	-0.8%	+0.6%
Torsional Stiffness	-1.5%	+1.1%

LOADCASE OPTIMISATION

Following the Phase 3 baseline analyses, the design was modified so that the stress levels in the structure were below the target allowable levels. Allowable stresses were taken as a fraction of the ultimate failure stress. The relevant fraction was dependent on the load case. The design was iteratively modified using separate models for abuse, crash, roof crush, seatbelt pull and durability loadcases. The use of separate models allowed the most significant loadcases to be identified as well as speeding up the process by allowing the design iterations to be performed in parallel.

For each iterative modification, regions of high stress were highlighted and the surrounding material was reinforced as appropriate. The analysis was then rerun and the results were rechecked. This process continued until the stress was reduced to below allowable levels.

It was found that each loadcase required reinforcement in specific areas of the structure. The abuse loads (door sag, door closure and door over-opening) meant that both the lower A and B-pillars required local thickening. The front crash loadcase resulted in thickening of large areas at the front of the vehicle, particularly around the longitudes, wheel arches and upper and lower A-pillar. Seat belt pull loads resulted in thickening of the areas adjacent to each of the mount positions, the tunnel, the

sill at the base of the B-pillar and the upper B-pillar. The roof crush loadcase resulted in some local thickening of the roof and the cantrail between the A and B-pillars. It was found that the durability loadcases were satisfied by the reinforcement applied for the crash and abuse cases.

FINAL VERIFICATION

The final Phase 3 verification analysis was performed once all of the separate models used for individual loadcase optimisation were shown to meet allowable levels for stress. The models were combined by taking the maximum material thickness in a particular area, from the individual loadcases, and updating the master model. This was done to verify that the overall design still met the targets for allowable stress under all loadcases. The final verification also showed that the models had been combined correctly and was reanalysed using all of the loadcases and the results were verified to ensure that all values were within the acceptable allowable range.

- Stiffness
- Torsion and Bending
- Front Crash
- Initial Impact, 170mm & 340mm Crush
- Roof Crush
- Seat Belt Pull
- Durability
- Front and Rear Pothole Bump
- Maximum and Corner Bump
- Panic, Durability and Reverse Braking
- High G and Limit Cornering
- Kerb Push Off
- Lateral Kerb Strike
- Front and Rear Pothole Braking
- Front and Rear Oblique Kerb Strike
- Abuse Loads
- Door sag – Door Closed
- Door Over-open
- Modal Analysis Un-massed BIW
- First global torsion mode
- First global bending

INSERTS

Simple representations of the significant structural inserts were included in the BIW model. The main function of the inserts in this model is to allow added mass and suspension loads to be spread into the BIW in a representative manner. The inserts were offset from the BIW panel elements by 0.5mm and ‘bonded’ to the structure.

The adhesive was modelled using bar elements (Nastran CBARs) positioned at the facing nodes of elements over the insert. The bar elements were aligned to lie normal to the carbon panels to ensure the axial and shear loads recovered in the element was a true reflection of the local components of load. The fixed mesh density along and across the flanges meant that each flange element was nominally the same area. This allowed the adhesive properties to be constant for all the adhesive elements and based on a proportion of the nominal flange element area.

DETAILED INSERT ANALYSIS

During the feasibility stage of FP3 it was deemed necessary to undertake detailed analysis on some key inserts. PTC Pro/Mechanica was used to model, load and analyse the insert and local surrounding structure.

The PTC Pro/Mechanica software used in this study features P-type elements in its solution of structural problems. Unlike conventional H-type finite element models, the accuracy of the adaptive P-type geometric solutions are not directly affected by the number of elements within a model.

Additionally, P-type element edges are not faceted, permitting the geometry of curved surfaces to be fully modelled, thus accurately capturing stress concentrations in features such as fillets. In the solution, the polynomial order of the elements selectively increases allowing the model to converge to a specified tolerance.

This modelling technique allows the detailed stress levels to be determined in the adhesive itself, leading to a full understanding of the local stress field, and allows development of the joint to reduce the damaging local high stress areas.

The analysis is linear static, using loads from the BIW analysis, or loads applied directly to the model via simplified external structure, as is the case for the suspension, where links are modelled as beams.

FRONT CRASH INVESTIGATIONS

Due to deficiencies in non-linear dynamic FEA codes for composite material crash prediction, front crush and roof crush were investigated using inertial relief techniques to estimate the additional material mass required for a crashworthy passenger cell structure. The full dynamic effects of the impact are not completely addressed with this approach but by employing knockdown factors of 33% for material strength, reasonable estimates for the robustness of the backup structure are assumed

Composites absorb energy by a very different mechanism to metallic structures, which is an important consideration in designing a composite vehicle. Metallic structures absorb energy by plastic folding of the metal, initiated by local buckling of the structure. Composites absorb energy by local crushing of the material, by matrix cracking, fibre buckling and fracture and frictional heating. Unlike metallic structures, the crushed composite material has no residual strength after absorbing energy. This requires that the crushing of a composite car be controlled to always have the crushed material at the interface to the barrier. If failure occurs in the structure away from the barrier, considerable energy absorption capability is lost. Stability of the structure may also be compromised. It is also important to note that the crushed composite structure is totally destroyed and essentially takes up no volume, therefore more package space can be used in absorbing the impact energy, compared to a metallic car.

FEATURES DESIRED IN DESIGN

The philosophy followed for the impact performance of the vehicle has been to separate the functions of energy absorption from the safety cell. The safety cell has been designed to be strong enough to withstand the forces generated in the impact without failure. The energy absorbing element of the structure is required to absorb the impact energy by controlled crush of the material in contact with the barrier. It is important that the material is crushed at the barrier interface. Any failure behind this point renders the material between the barrier and the failure redundant due to the total lack of residual strength of the failed material. The crush members have to be as straight as possible to allow the crush required, and they must have good lateral stability. It is also desirable to have the energy absorbing element able to spread the impact forces into as much of the safety cell as possible.

To facilitate the impact event to occur the under bonnet package has been designed to ensure that hard to crush items are packaged in appropriate locations to prevent stack up. These more rigid items contribute to either damage or premature failure of the energy absorbing elements or intrusion into the passenger compartment.

HOW THE DESIGN MEETS THESE REQUIREMENTS

After considering many possible structures the chosen design was adopted. Discrete crush members are the dominant feature of the design, and are chosen to address the requirements as follows.

The compact box sections provide the stable crush due to the stability provided by the corners of the box section. Cored flat sections were discarded for crushing, due to a number of factors. Foam cores do not crush into a small volume and therefore inhibit stable crushing. Honeycomb cores in aluminium or similar materials that do crush well, but would add considerable cost. Box sections are favoured by the difficult packaging requirements of the engine, suspension and exterior styling. They can also be load bearing for engine and suspension attachment fulfilling two structural roles. Box sections are easily incorporated into the rest of the structure.

The upper longitudinal is aligned with the bodyside structure which is itself a very substantial component. Also in an overload event the longitudinal is not forced directly into the passenger compartment, compromising the integrity of the safety cell.

The lower longitudinal connects directly into the floor which is reinforced with a cross member at the floor firewall interface. The joint of the lower longitudinal is a tapered joint to introduce a degree of compression into the adhesive joint, to improve strength in impact conditions. A tapered front to the longitudinal reduces the initial crush forces again to minimise the shock loading into the adhesive.

The two longitudinals are joined vertically by the inner panel, which provides vertical strength for stability of the upper longitudinal. This panel may need to be corrugated to provide vertical buckling resistance, although there is a substantial swage toward the rear for the engine mountings and also the radiator cowl provides buckling resistance in the early part of the impact event. Corrugating this inner panel would also reduce any tendency for the adhesive to fracture along the joint between the panel and the longitudinals in impact, so maintaining the stability provided by the panel throughout the impact event. The corrugations will crush locally when impacted by the bumper beam without affecting the vertical stability of the longitudinals.

Finally all the major inserts are positioned outside of the crush zone to avoid reducing the efficiency of the energy absorbing components.

CRASH RESULTS

The predicted crash pulse for the FP3 BIW is shown in the following figure, superimposed on that for the JA vehicle. The longitudinals absorb approximately 55% of the total kinetic energy of the vehicle.

As the impact progresses the following events occur

- Total crush distance 760 mm
- Total impact time 79 ms
- Crush in longitudinals 506 mm
- Engine contacts wall after 22 ms
- Tyre contacts wall at 45 ms
- Engine contacts firewall at 70 ms
- Peak load in the upper longitudinal is 51.5 kN
- Peak load in the lower longitudinal is 32 kN

CONCLUSIONS

The structural, mass and cost objectives of the Focal Project 3 are feasible. The manufacturing of the components and the assembly are achievable with technology in the foreseeable future. The three phases of the project have proven to be important in the continued development of the performance and manufacturing objectives. Phase 1 set the foundations for the achievement. The concepts were evaluated and demonstrated an 80% and 200% improvement in bending and torsional efficiency over a stiffness optimised carbon BIW based on the production JA geometry.

The second phase of the project gave good indications that the targets would be met and also identified opportunities for development of the front end package for crash stability and improved durability of the strut tower.

The final phase of the project involved significantly greater analysis input than originally expected, due to the need to repeat the optimisation entirely on the developed phase three structure.

The primary structure needs to be carbon in order to realise the performance and mass objectives. Moving to a hybrid structure composed of carbon and glass or metallic sub-assemblies was considered inappropriate. Every effort has been taken to achieve an integrated and stable front-end design for crash. Incorporating a metallic crush structure would compromise this. In addition thermal expansion, extra weight of the connection and the weight of the crushable elements would almost certainly take us beyond our target mass.

Complete Model Showing Different Materials

The weight of the structure is controlled heavily by the minimum thickness of material. The studies have shown that increasing the minimum thickness beyond the 1.5 mm allowable would quickly reduce the mass reduction potential we have achieved. Manufacturing processes will need to be developed in order to cost effectively achieve panels with a 1.5 mm thickness and panels which allow for variable thickness throughout the part. This is a challenge to current processing technology, but certainly is not beyond the foreseeable development horizon.

Core is only required in the BIW for the cabin and boot floors and the roof. Polyurethane core is proposed due to its low cost, good bonding qualities, consistency and for the roof its mould ability.

Article	Mass (kg)
Chopped Carbon* Material	54.83
Woven Carbon* Fabric Material	17.73
Core Material	3.21
Adhesive	1.58
Analysed Inserts	6.41
Additional Inserts	2.39
TOTAL	86.15

Accessing relevant material information has been a major limitation during the project, particular with respect to the degradation in material performance with respect to reasonable operating conditions. In order to further the development of a production BIW, this data will need to be acquired for the material systems that can be reasonably represent the architectures of the production intent BIW.

The BIW structure has been optimised such that the passenger safety structure can react to the crash loadings in a stable manner and retain structural integrity with regard to intrusion from the engine compartment package. Finite element based numerical analysis techniques are in their infancy (but showing promise), but the task of predicting the performance of this structure using them is still some way in the future. Until such time, the analysis and development of this kind of structure needs to be based on proven principles from other composite structures and dynamic crush testing of the materials is required. The FP3 BIW structure has developed using methods and calculations that have been demonstrated on many racing car structures with great success.

The performance of the bonded longitudinal may be significantly affected through the use peel stopping rivets. The analysis suggests the adhesive is within the allowable limits throughout the crash event, however, the advancing crush front may stimulate a unzipping of the bonded seam with undesirable results. This could be avoided through crack arresting design detail. The option to use rivets should be maintained until this phenomenon has been investigated further. Tuning the crash pulse for this structure should be easily achieved once adequate material data is available.

RECOMMENDATIONS

PROCESSING

Concentrate fundamental research on producing 1.0 to 1.5 mm minimum thickness carbon panels with up to 10 mm of selectively placed localised reinforcement. These panels need to achieve complex geometry with high fibre volumes and predictable mechanical properties.

Investigate methods of introducing core and inserts into the chopped carbon mouldings.

Bodyside Thickness Plot

Regions of Different Lay-up in Floor

MATERIALS TESTING

In order to develop confidence in the performance of composite vehicle structures at the design stage, a considerable amount of materials testing should be undertaken. The information currently available is inadequate, particularly with respect to the degradation in material performance with simulated usage. The testing should be focussed on material systems that show production promise. Where these are identified but not available, alternative architectures that show similar characteristics should be considered in order to accelerate the acquisition process.

The decision on which processing methodology is appropriate for the components will need to consider the through life performance characteristics.

Adhesives should also be included in the testing programme; they are critical to the success of a composite intensive BIW. The information available now is insufficient. Priority needs to be given to developing a consistent and relevant set of testing procedures for the properties needed for the development of a BIW.

Generic Properties

Stiffness, static strength, dynamic crush performance and compatibility with adhesives are the main factors needed at the onset of selection of material. A selected set of tests should be developed to allow these properties to be quickly determined and rated against other materials. This will allow for early screening of properties to determine whether degraded test programmes should be initiated.

Durability

The performance of a composite structure will degrade over its life. How much the performance will degrade, what are the most important accelerators for the degradation, and which properties are most affected will need assessing before vehicles can be brought to the market.

Degradation will take two principal paths, environmental ageing and loading related degradation. Both will need some degree of assessment, individually and with combined effect. Efforts to study the durability performance of composites are underway at the Oak Ridge National Laboratory [Corum].

The environmental effects will include temperature, moisture and UV cycling over a period of time.

Loading related degradation is more complex than environment and will need to be carefully constructed in order to provide useful information for design analysis and for rating materials against each other at an early stage. Fatigue, abuse, sub-critical impact and local overload are all loading scenarios that are likely to degrade the performance of a structure, without producing observable indications.

Adhesives

In addition to the above degradation testing the adhesives will need to have further considerations. Manufacturing consistency is a big concern with adhesives and tolerance to modified cure cycles should be considered.

Unlike the structural attributes of the laminate, adhesives need to work in conjunction with different materials. There will often be a requirement for dissimilar materials to be bonded together. The performance of an adhesive must therefore be tested with different materials as they are selected for more detailed process development.

CRASH

Simulated production materials in component, sub-assembly and full BIW configurations should be tested to support the programme to develop non-linear dynamic analysis techniques for future vehicles. This information will act as a qualified source of real and relevant results that the explicit codes will need to achieve before attempting to develop real structures.

FUTURE EFFORTS

Based on the recommendations of this study and the specific results of the analysis portion of the focal project, the team has identified critical materials and processing developments necessary to go forward in order to build a demonstration part that meets the program's objectives. Key manufacturing requirements include:

- Minimum thickness of 1.5 mm in large complex parts
- Fibre volume fraction of at least 40% for random chopped carbon composites
- Low variability in material properties within a part
- Significant variations in section thickness within a part – 1.5 mm to 8 mm with low material scrap rates
- Short molding cycle times to achieve desired production rates

In order to achieve these manufacturing requirements, the team has built a learning tool to develop the necessary preforming and molding technology. This part includes representative features of the full body side allowing for processing developments to be done with a smaller less expensive tool. Once the group has developed the necessary materials, processing, and joining technology required by the body side, the full body side will be built to demonstrate the high volume process.

Cost modeling efforts are also underway to quantify the cost-efficiency of the design, which is based on low-scrap, highly automated processes as well as low-cost carbon fibres. This is being utilized to identify the most cost effective processes to consider. These technology developments are being undertaken within the ACC/DOE collaborative research program as well.

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